
5G EVE

5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials

Deliverable D5.9

**Testing, validation, and performance
diagnosis methodologies user manual**

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
API	Application Programming Interface
BMU	Best Matching Unit
CtxB	Context Blueprint
DL	Downlink
DN	Data Network
E2E	End-to- End
EEM	Experiment Execution Manager
ELM	Experiment Lifecycle Manager
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ExpB	Experiment Blueprint
FSM	Finite State Machine
gNB	Next-generation NodeB
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
IP	Internet Protocol
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
IWF	Interworking Framework
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MAC	Medium Access Control
MEF	Metrics Extractor Function
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communication
ML	Machine Learning
NG-RAN	Next Generation Radio Access Network
OTT	One-Trip Time
PD	Performance Diagnosis
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAV	Results Analysis and Validation
RC	Runtime Configuration
RCA	Root Cause Analysis
REST	Representational State Transfer
RTT	Round-Trip Time

<i>SLA</i>	Service Level Agreement
<i>SOM</i>	Self-Organizing Maps
<i>TCB</i>	TestCase Blueprint
<i>UC</i>	Use Case
<i>UE</i>	User Equipment
<i>UL</i>	Uplink
<i>URLLC</i>	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
<i>VNF</i>	Virtual Network Function
<i>VR</i>	Virtual Reality
<i>VS</i>	Vertical Service Blueprint

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Executive Summary

In deliverable D5.9, the user manual of the final 5G EVE testing and validation methodology and framework is presented. This user manual provides details on the step-by-step procedure to design, prepare, instantiate, execute and validate an experiment and further collect insights from the performance diagnosis process.

Deliverable D5.9 is structured as follows: in the main body of the deliverable the overall approach and all the procedures are explained in brief with appropriate references to the Annex. In the Annexes these procedures are explained in detail following a step-by-step user manual fashion.

Deliverable D5.9 covers all the 5G EVE testing and validation processes including:

- Appropriate procedures to be followed to design, prepare and execute an experiment on the 5G EVE platform.
- Validation procedures presenting the steps necessary for the validation of the experiment's KPIs.
- Diagnostics procedures, presenting the steps required for the activation and utilisation of the 5G EVE performance diagnosis tool.

1 Introduction

Deliverable D5.9 presents the user manual of the final 5G EVE testing and validation methodology and framework. In the current section, the 5G EVE testing and validation framework is briefly presented, while the structure of the document is explained in section 1.2.

1.1 5G EVE testing and validation framework

The 5G EVE testing and validation framework architecture is illustrated in Figure 1. In this figure, the overall architecture is presented including components from all the 5G EVE technical WPs (WP2/WP3/WP4/WP5) as well as the relation of WP5 modules with the rest of the 5G EVE components. In detail, WP2 modules appear in grey colour, WP3 modules appear in yellow colour, while those of WP4 appear in green and those of WP5 in red. The colour of the different arrows shows the allocation of the module that starts the communication.

Figure 1: 5G EVE testing and validation framework architecture

As depicted in Figure 1, three are the key modules that WP5 has defined as part of the 5G EVE Test and Validation framework. These are the “Experiment Execution Manager”, the “Results Analysis and Validation” and the “Performance Diagnosis” components. Together with these three components, also a “Tests Scripts Inventory” has been included to store the different scripts associated with different Test Cases.

The final version of the 5G EVE testing and validation framework, as well as details on all the aforementioned WP5 modules are presented in D5.8 [5].

The current document serves as a user manual for the use of the overall 5G EVE testing and validation framework focusing on the WP5 related modules.

1.2 Document structure

D5.9 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 briefly presents the appropriate procedures to be followed to design, prepare and execute an experiment on the 5G EVE platform. In addition, in Annex A this description is extended by providing further details on the step-by-step procedure to design, prepare, instantiate, and execute an experiment, as part of 5G EVE User Manual.
- In Section 3, the steps necessary for the validation of the experiment's KPIs are presented. In the main body of the section, the validation procedures are presented, while in Annex A these procedures are explained in detail following a step-by-step user manual fashion.
- In Section 4, the steps required for the preparation and activation of the Performance diagnosis tool for a selected experiment are presented. Similar to Section 3, in the main body the procedures are summarised, while in Annex A the related procedures are presented as a step-by-step user guide.
- Finally, Section 5 summarises the document.

2 Experiment design, preparation and execution

The overall 5G EVE experimentation approach is illustrated in Figure 2. It presents the workflow of the overall process, which is followed including the test design, preparation, execution, analysis and KPI validation steps.

Figure 2: 5G EVE testing and validation approach

In this section, we focus and explain briefly the steps to be taken to design, prepare and execute an experiment on the 5G EVE platform. Further details on the step-by-step procedure to design, prepare, instantiate, and execute an experiment on the portal can be found in the 5G EVE User Manual, presented in Annex A of the current document.

2.1 Experiment design

To design an experiment on the portal, the 5G EVE platform takes advantage of different blueprints [1][2]: Vertical Service Blueprints (VSB), Context Blueprints (CtxBs), Test Case Blueprints (TCBs), and the Experiment Blueprint (ExpB). These blueprints are high-level deployment templates to assist the verticals in designing their experiments. Consequently, each blueprint except the TCB is accompanied by a corresponding Network Service Descriptor, a lower-level deployment template defining how the experiment and the related service components must be deployed and executed on the platform. In the next section, we summarize the VNF images' preparation, descriptors' design, and onboarding stages on the 5G EVE platform.

2.1.1 VNF images preparation and onboarding

The first step for a vertical to design and execute an experiment on the platform is to prepare the virtual network function (VNF) images and the physical network functions (PNFs) to be used in the experiment. This preparation could include:

- Installation and configuration of the necessary software packages of the VNFs and PNFs to support the use case.
- Creation and saving of the VNF images.
- Configuration of the PNFs network interfaces to ensure connectivity to the VNFs launched from the portal.
- Creation of the VNF and PNF descriptors and uploading these descriptors to the 5G EVE VNF catalogue; these VNF packages will be later onboarded to the 5G EVE site where the experiment is to be deployed.

More details on the portal VNF onboarding process can be found in section A.2 of the current document.

2.1.2 Blueprints and Network Service Descriptors Design

As earlier mentioned, to define an experiment on the platform, the experimenter (Exp)/vertical together with the experiment developer, must design the following blueprints [1][2]:

- Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB): This blueprint is used to define the main features of the experiment. It includes (i) Atomic components, (ii) Connection and Service Access endpoints, (iii) Virtual links and their associated connection points, (iv) Use case application metrics to be collected, and (v) the 5G EVE site (s) where the experiment will be instantiated and monitored. A corresponding network service descriptor accompanies this VSB.
- Context Blueprints (CtxBs): The experimenters use this blueprint to add network impairments, e.g., delay and packet loss, to their experiments. This blueprint, too, is followed by a corresponding network service descriptor.
- Test Case Blueprints (TCBs): These blueprints are used to test the functionality of the Vertical use case after it has been successfully instantiated on the portal. The vertical defines their use case tests inside this blueprint.
- Experiment blueprint: This blueprint combines the VSB, CtxBs, TCBs, KPIs, and any infrastructure metrics associated with the experiment. The use case KPI thresholds are defined in this blueprint. This blueprint is also accompanied by a corresponding NSD.

More details on the descriptors' design can be found in section **A.3** of the present document.

2.1.3 Onboarding of the Descriptors to the 5G EVE platform

After designing the blueprints and network service descriptors for the experiment, the vertical can then upload them into the portal [1][2]:

- Initially, the VSB and its corresponding NSD are uploaded into the portal.
- In case the experiment utilizes some CtxBs, these are uploaded next together with the corresponding NSDs.
- Thirdly, all the TCBs associated with the use case are onboarded.
- Finally, the ExpB is created on the portal using the ExpB wizard by selecting the required VSB, CtxB, and TCBs. In addition, the use case KPIs and infrastructure metrics are defined in this blueprint. A corresponding NSD also accompanies this blueprint.

More details on the descriptor onboarding process can be found in section **A.4** of the present document.

2.2 Experiment preparation

After designing and onboarding the experiment descriptors into the portal, the next step is to prepare an experiment on the portal; this preparation involves requesting an experiment on the portal by (i) Creating the experiment descriptors and (ii) Scheduling an experiment [1][2]. More detail about the experiment preparation procedure can be found in section **A.5** of the present document.

2.2.1 Creation of the Experiment Descriptors

To instantiate the experiment on the portal, the user must customize the blueprints uploaded in Section **2.1.3** by specifying the values and ranges for each of the parameters defined in the blueprints. This process of blueprint customization to a specific instance of an experiment is achieved through the creation of the experiment descriptors. For the VSB and CtxB, this customization could involve such tasks as defining the ranges of the blueprint parameters. On the other hand, this customization could require providing the username and password and any other configuration parameter values for the TCB. For the ExpB, this customization may require defining the target thresholds for evaluating each of the KPIs defined in the ExpB. More details are provided in D4.3 [6].

2.2.2 Schedule and Instantiate an experiment

After creating the experiment descriptors, the next step is to schedule an experiment on the portal. This scheduling involves selecting the applicable Experiment descriptor (defined previously), the use case, and the dates on which the vertical wants to perform the experiment.

Once an experiment schedule request has been made on the portal, this request is sent to the site-manager of the requested 5G EVE site. On receiving this request and agreeing to the request, the site manager makes the necessary configurations to accommodate the new experiment. Once the site is ready, the vertical is notified, and from here onwards, they can proceed to instantiate their experiment. More detail is available in sections **0**, **A.8**, and **A.9**.

2.3 Experiment execution

Once the experiment has been successfully instantiated on the portal, the vertical can proceed to execute the experiment.

On executing their experiment, the vertical is presented with another opportunity to customize their test parameters further. On setting these parameters, the vertical can proceed to execute and validate their experiment.

If the execution is successful, the user will be able to view their metrics and the KPI validation report in the portal.

More detail about the 5G EVE experiment execution process is available in **A.9** whereas information regarding the portal Metrics and KPI monitoring tools can be found in section **A.10**.

Additionally, more information about the experimentation portal can be accessed in D4.4 [1] and D4.6 [2].

3 Experiment validation

In this section, we briefly describe the steps necessary for the validation of the experiment's KPIs. Since the validation process is automated and non-interactive, the input required from the vertical is presented as well as the generated validation report structure.

3.1 KPI definition and selection

To correctly perform the validation of an experiment's KPIs, the vertical must provide the necessary information during the experiment design stage. This is done using the form shown in Figure 3 and A.4.3, in Figure 52.

Figure 3: 5G EVE Experiment Blueprint Metrics & KPIs Section

This input is split into two categories:

- A list of metrics that will be generated and monitored during the experiment's execution. A list of infrastructure metrics is supported on all the sites. Application metrics are also supported but must be specified both in this list and inside the VSB, with suitable data shippers installed in the service's VNF images to collect and distribute such metrics to the 5G EVE monitoring platform. If the list of metrics is empty, then the validation process will be skipped as there is no input data to ingest.
- A list of KPIs to be calculated and validated after the experiment has finished. These KPIs use one or multiple metrics from the list as inputs and a formula for the calculation. Supported formulas are all typical mathematical expressions using the names of the input metrics as variables. If the list of KPIs is empty, the validation process will be executed for the provided inputs but since no KPIs were provided the validation results will be empty.

For each metric, the required information pertains to the type of metric, the collection interval, a unique id, its name, its measurement unit and the way to be graphed, i.e., the graph type, on the monitoring platform. For each of the provided KPIs, similarly a name, unique id, unit, calculation interval, and graph type are needed. For the calculation of the KPIs additional information is needed and provided with a few extra fields. Those are the metrics ids list, which is a list of metrics, their ids, to be used as input for the formula that will calculate the KPI value, and a formula, the expression that will use the inputs to calculate the KPI value. If the formula is left empty or includes only an input's name, it is assumed that the KPI mirrors its input and so the input values are published directly as the KPI values. The list of parameters for the metrics and KPIs can be seen in Table 1 and in A.4.3, Table 4.

Table 1: Metrics and KPIs parameter list

Part 1- Metrics		
Parameter Type	Description	Comments
Metric Type	Type of the metric you want to measure	Current possible values [LOST_PKT, RECEIVED_PKT, SENT_PKT, LATENCY, BANDWIDTH]
Interval	The time interval by which you want to measure your metric	Depends on the metric you are considering
Collection Type	Metric collection method	Current possible values [CUMULATIVE, DELTA, GAUGE]
Metric Id	Id of your metric	uuid format
Graph Type	Type of Graph to use to display the metric	Current possible values [LINE, PIE, COUNTER, GAUGE]
Name	Name of the metric	
Unit	Standard SI Unit in which the metric is to be measured	For time-related metrics, this could be “s” for seconds and “ms” for milliseconds
<i>To add more metrics, please click on the “+” icon</i>		
Part 2 – KPIs		
Parameter Type	Description	Comments
Formula	Formula/Equation to compute your KPIs	In case your KPI is as a result of applying some sort of operation(s)/formula to the collected metrics. Otherwise, if your KPI is the same as the collected metric, then in that case just put the metric name as the formula.
Interval	Interval at which this KPI should be computed	Depends on the KPIs you are looking at
KPI Id	Id of your KPI	uuid format
Graph Type	Type of Graph to use to display the KPI	Current possible values [LINE, PIE, COUNTER, GAUGE]
Name	Name of the KPI	
Unit	Standard SI Unit of the KPI	For time related KPIs, this could be “s” for seconds and “ms” for milliseconds
Metric Ids	Ids of the metrics you want to consider for this KPI	Add all the metric ids of the metrics used for this KPI. These metrics should be related to the formula given above
<i>To add more metrics, please click on the “+” icon</i>		

After this list is filled, the next necessary information for the validation are the validation conditions, meaning an acceptable range for the values of the calculated KPIs. These can be a range, upper bound and lower bound, or a single limit, upper or lower. These are also provided by the vertical during the Request Experiment stage using the form shown in A.5.1 in Figure 65.

3.2 Reporting

The validation report generated after the experiment execution is finished, consists of separate segments that present information generated during the execution and the results analysis and validation workflow. In this report the vertical can see an overview of the experiment information, like:

- A list of the experiments executed by this vertical.
- Execution and completion date/time of the selected experiment.
- The site where it was deployed.
- The KPIs selected and their validation conditions.
- The testcases that were executed.
- Statistics for the KPI that were validated.
- The KPI performance during the whole execution.

An overview of the report can be seen in Figure 4. These segments are presented with more details in 0.

Figure 4: Validation report overview

Additionally, more information about the experiment validation processes can be accessed in D5.3 [3] and D5.8 [5].

4 Performance diagnosis tool

In this section, we describe the steps necessary for the preparation and activation of the Performance diagnosis on an examined experiment. The diagnosis process is automated and non-interactive in order to provide a more simplified experience for all verticals in case some are not familiar with the terminology, operations and actions required. The input as well as the configuration conventions required from the vertical are presented along with the generated validation report structure.

4.1 Preparation and activation

For the vertical to perform a performance diagnosis on an experiment execution, there are two conditions that must be met. First, a few naming conventions must be honoured during the experiment design and creation and second the performance diagnosis must be enabled when executing the experiment.

During the design stage the following conventions must be honoured:

- The naming of the nodes of a NS should be consistent across all Blueprints, Descriptors, hosts, and probes generating the metrics. This assures that the topology information can be retrieved and processed correctly.
- Additionally, the name of the node should also appear on the flavour id field of the VSB NSD descriptor, usually followed by a typical “_df” or “_flavour” suffix.
- The metric names should also include as a prefix this node name in order to correctly match the generated messages to the topology elements.

Using as an example the classic testing use case, an Apache server and client, applying these naming conventions results in the node name “apache_client_vnf” in the VSB, NSD, and device_id in the probe configuration, as well as “apache_client_vnf_flavour” flavourId property of the corresponding component in the NSD. Also, the application metrics declared in the VSB are prefixed with the same name, creating the full metric name “apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken”. Additionally, if there are multiple data flow paths in the service, adding a “_src_” and “_dst_” designation on specific node names can help target the specific data flow for the RCA. If these designations are missing, then a more generic version of the RCA will execute taking into consideration all the available nodes.

After all configurations are finished and the experiment is ready to be executed, upon execution the Vertical can select the flag on the Portal GUI to enable the performance diagnosis using the corresponding option, as seen in 0, in Figure 108. Due to the lack of a priori information for each experiment examined, mostly because of the ability to alter the configurations for different executions, the neural network models, used to identify the status of the nodes based on the metrics and the root cause of possible anomalies, are trained, and evaluated during the performance diagnosis workflow. The data generated during an execution that is validated successfully are used in order to train the model even further, while the data from an execution that failed to validate will only be evaluated using the models. The only exception is the first execution, which is set to train by default in order to generate the initial model. This technique allows the models to increase their detection accuracy much faster than simply using all the executions disregarding their outcome.

After the experiment has finished, the collected data are fed to the diagnosis algorithms, analysed and the validation report is enriched with the performance diagnosis results.

4.2 Reporting

After the performance diagnosis operations are finished, the results are added to the validation report to produce the final conclusive report regarding the experiment. The new information added on the report are:

- A timeline of the performance of each node of the NS based on the metrics it generated during the experiment execution.
- A topology graph displaying the status of each node at each examined timestamp.

- For each of these timestamps, detailed analytic information is provided as well as list of probable root causes if any performance degradation was detected. The impact of each monitored metric/KPI is also displayed, making it obvious as to which specific metric caused the anomaly detection algorithm to flag it.
- A graph comparing the performance of the selected KPIs of this experiment on different resources. This option is available when the same experiment (service) has been executed using different flavours (resources) for the VNFs instantiated. This graph can provide insights as to what performance increase or decrease can be achieved by modifying the number of resources allocated for the examined service. It works as a kind of profiling for the service.

It is clear from the results of the performance diagnosis tool and the reports generated, that the raw data generated during the experiment is the source of all these insights. So, a functionality is provided by the 5G EVE portal in order to allow the experimenter access to this data. This is achieved using an API to directly interface with the DCS and retrieve the desired data. The detailed steps to follow in order to achieve that is described in A.10.1.

Figure 5: Performance diagnosis results overview for example use case

As an example, the performance diagnosis executed on a classic use case used for testing, using an Apache server and client, is shown in Figure 5. Additional information regarding each segment is presented with more details in 0.

Additionally, more information about the performance diagnosis tool can be accessed in D5.5 [4].

5 Conclusions

In this deliverable, the user manual for testing, validation and diagnosis of an experiment is illustrated. In the main body of the document, all the required procedures for the design, preparation, execution, validation and performance diagnosis of an experiment are presented in brief, since all the details are already provided in the related deliverables (D4.3 [6], D4.4 [1], D4.6 [2], D5.3 [3], D5.5 [4] and D5.8 [5]) and the 5G EVE Portal User Manual [7].

In addition, in the main body of the document references to Annex A are included, in which the actual user manual is presented. In Annex A, the full user manual is presented, illustrating in a step-by-step fashion all the required details for: a) execution and validation of an experiment (related with WP5), b) use of the performance diagnosis tool on an experiment (related with WP5) and c) design and preparation of an experiment (related with WP4, but provided also here for completeness).

References

- [1] 5G EVE D4.4, “Report on benchmarking of new features and on the experiment portal (2nd version)”, June 2020, <https://zenodo.org/record/3946283#.YJlo46GEZPY>
- [2] 5G EVE D4.6, “Final version of the experimentation portal”, May 2021.
- [3] 5G EVE D5.3: “Testing environmental conditions document with first version of testing and validation suite”, June 2020, <https://zenodo.org/record/3946265#.YILsWugzaUk>
- [4] 5G EVE D5.5 “Performance diagnosis mechanism and reporting methodology document”, June 2020, <https://zenodo.org/record/3946255#.YILsW-gzaUk>
- [5] 5G EVE D5.8 “Testing and validation methodologies final report with the final version of testing and validation suite”, April 2021.
- [6] 5G EVE D4.3 “Models for vertical descriptor adaptation”, April 2020, <https://zenodo.org/record/4311316#.YK5Y-aGEZPY>
- [7] 5G EVE “5G EVE Portal User Manual”, December 2020, https://www.it.uc3m.es/jgr/5G-EVE/5G_EVE_Portal_User_Manual.pdf

ANNEX

A.5G EVE PORTAL USER GUIDE

A.1. REGISTRATION ON THE PLATFORM

- To register on the platform, go to the login page of the portal at <https://portal.5g-eve.eu/#/login>. Once there click on the “Register” button as indicated in Figure 6:

Figure 6: Login page

- On clicking the “Register” button, you will be provided with a page similar to the one shown in Figure 7:

Figure 7: Registration page

- Fill in your registration details and click on submit; all fields are compulsory.
- On clicking submit, your registration request will be sent to the 5G EVE administrators in charge of authentication on the platform. Therefore, this registration is not automatic, i.e., you will not be given instant access upon registration, but only after your role on the 5G EVE platform has been confirmed accordingly.
- Once your registration has been successful, you will receive a notification email. Henceforth, you can proceed to use the 5G EVE platform to design, run and execute your experiments.

A.2. ONBOARDING OF VNF PACKAGES

- The main objective of VNF provider actors is to upload the VNF packages associated to the Vertical Service that other actors will use to run on the platform.
- To this end, the 5G EVE platform provides the “VNF Onboard tool”. This tool can be used to onboard VNF packages (i.e., images, VNF descriptors, and metadata, etc.) to the 5G EVE platform.
- So, depending on the requirements of the Management and Network Orchestration (MANO) platform of the specific 5G EVE site(s) where experiment and experiment developers want to deploy their experiments, these VNF packages can be uploaded using this tool.
- To be able to onboard your VNF package to the platform, you need to prepare the following files/folders:
 - i) VNF Image: this is the actual base image of your VNF, saved in the preferable format for the considered MANO platform.
 - ii) VNF descriptor: this should be a zipped folder containing your VNF descriptor package.
 - iii) Any additional requisite files depending on the MANO platform under consideration.
- Once these files have been prepared, zip the files into a single folder (the acceptable zip format is “.zip”); subsequently, we can proceed to upload the zipped VNF folder to the platform using the VNF Onboard tool.
- To use the tool, go to the portal and login with the email address and password you provided during the registration procedure. Upon logging in, you will be provided with the portal home page shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: 5G EVE portal home page

- Go ahead and click on the “Design Experiments” tab. Once inside, select the “Virtual Network Functions list” tab as illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: VNF Onboarding tool

- On clicking on the “Virtual Network Functions list” tab, you will be redirected to a page similar to the one given in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Select VNF Onboard tool

- Go ahead and click on the “Onboard VNFs” tab and you will see a page similar to the one in Figure 11.

Figure 11: VNF Onboarding tool

- This tool provides four main functionalities:

- i) VNF Uploading and creation of deployment requests (represented by the “Upload VNF” tab in Figure 11): used to upload the VNF packages.
 - ii) Created VNF Deployment requests list (represented by the “Deployment Requests” tab in Figure 11): used to upload the VNF package to the MANO platform of the specified 5G EVE site.
 - iii) Uploaded VNFs List (represented by the “My VNFs” tab in Figure 11): used to display a list of your uploaded VNFs and supports a re-deployment of the same VNF to different 5G EVE sites.
 - iv) Update VNF list (represented by the “Update List” button in Figure 11): this button is used to force the update of the VNF deployment requests list in case the VNF list is not automatically updated.
- These four functionalities are discussed further in the following sections.

A.2.1. VNF Uploading and creation of deployment requests

- To upload your VNF package, click on the “Upload VNF” tab in Figure 12. On clicking on this tab, you will be redirected to a page similar to **Figure 12**.

Figure 12: Upload VNF and Create Deployment Request

- In order to onboard your VNF package on the platform, follow the steps below:
 - i) Input the preferred name of your VNF file (indicated as step 1 in Figure 12);
 - ii) Next, click on the “select file” icon to upload your zipped VNF package folder i.e., containing all your VNF details (indicated as step 2 in Figure 12);
 - iii) Thirdly, select the 5G EVE site name where you want your VNF to be uploaded (indicated as step 3 in Figure 12);
 - iv) Finally, click on the “Upload File” button to upload your VNF package folder (indicated as step 4 in Figure 12).
- An example of a complete VNF Upload and deployment request is provided in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Complete VNF deployment request

A.2.2. Created VNF Deployment Requests List

- Once your VNF package has been successfully uploaded and the deployment request created, you can proceed to view the status of your deployment request using the “Deployment Requests” tab.
- For example, in Figure 14, we can view the recently uploaded VNF package in section A.2.1 called “simple_vnf.zip,” the 5G EVE site where the request was sent (in this case the “SPAIN_5TONIC” site), and its current status is “PENDING”; which means waiting for approval and deployment by the site manager of the “SPAIN_5TONIC” site.

Request ID	Filename	Associated Site	Status	Actions
d223891-e1ef-41e7-ba00-e061a3c4b5	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	FRANCE_RENNES	READY	🔍 🗑️
79f16d2-b6f3-4044-ed61-ca56be1056c3	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	GREECE_ATHENS	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
84a2a06-3a08-4083-a072-d8438790421e	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	ITALY_TURIN	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
d795748-5462-4b8d-b6d5-a43d805883e	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	ITALY_TURIN	READY	🔍 🗑️
34c8722-d867-4365-9729-474a718a787	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
0b23172f-2283-4049-9375-3577aa740609	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
ee04396-505c-463c-8a91-89e5f7161ea	VNF_test_upload_4.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
d780972-3841-48c1-1625-45e1a62650b0	VNF_test_upload_5.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
2c0ab88-062c-4879-a510-555ae0546d8	VNF_test_upload_10.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
a4236c67-4f40-4020-8d6c-5e367831c1d	simple_vnf.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️

Figure 14: Created Deployment Requests

- Once this deployment request is accepted by the site manager and your VNF package has been uploaded, the deployment status will change to “READY” as indicated in Figure 15. At this point, your VNF deployment request has been accepted, and will be available on the platform in due time.

Request ID	Filename	Associated Site	Status	Actions
d223891-e1ef-41e7-ba00-e061a3c4b5	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	FRANCE_RENNES	READY	🔍 🗑️
79f16d2-b6f3-4044-ed61-ca56be1056c3	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	GREECE_ATHENS	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
84a2a06-3a08-4083-a072-d8438790421e	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	ITALY_TURIN	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
d795748-5462-4b8d-b6d5-a43d805883e	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	ITALY_TURIN	READY	🔍 🗑️
34c8722-d867-4365-9729-474a718a787	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
0b23172f-2283-4049-9375-3577aa740609	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
ee04396-505c-463c-8a91-89e5f7161ea	VNF_test_upload_4.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
d780972-3841-48c1-1625-45e1a62650b0	VNF_test_upload_5.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
2c0ab88-062c-4879-a510-555ae0546d8	VNF_test_upload_10.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
a4236c67-4f40-4020-8d6c-5e367831c1d	simple_vnf.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	READY	🔍 🗑️

Figure 15: Accepted VNF Deployment Request

A.2.3. Uploaded VNFs List

- To view your Uploaded VNFs, click on the “My VNFs” tab as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Uploaded VNFs List

- As you can see from Figure 16, we can see our newly uploaded VNF i.e., simple_vnf.zip (indicated as step (1)) and also have the option of downloading it (indicated as step (2)).
- Next, if we wanted to upload this VNF to a second 5G EVE site for example, the “ITALY_TURIN” site, we click on the “arrow” button (indicated as step (3) in Figure 16) corresponding to the VNF we wish to re-deploy.
- On clicking on the “arrow” button, we are presented with a page similar to Figure 17 and we select the new 5G EVE site where we wish to re-deploy this VNF, in this particular case, we chose the “ITALY_TURIN” site, henceforth, we click on the “Create” button to submit the deployment request.

Figure 17: Re-deploy VNF request

- On creating the deployment request, we can view this request under the “Deployment Requests” tab as indicated Figure 18.

Request ID	Filename	Associated Site	Status	Actions
#f23851+e1ef417e5a05e4061a3c0f55	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	FRANCE_RENNES	READY	🗑️ 📄
789f16a206a734044a6a1ca0491056c3	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	GREECE_ATHENS	PENDING	🗑️ 📄
8042a06-3a84-4083-a072-08438795421e	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	ITALY_TURIN	PENDING	🗑️ 📄
6795748-5462-4b86-ba08-a433080883e	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	ITALY_TURIN	READY	🗑️ 📄
0b470a03-7451-4a8b-ac23-0b6598102463	simple_vnf.zip	ITALY_TURIN	PENDING	🗑️ 📄
34c8772d-48e7-43e5-9729-476a778a7987	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	🗑️ 📄
0b231720-2283-40e9-9375-057aa740609	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	🗑️ 📄
ee048598-8b9c-463c-8a91-89e0577011a	VNF_test_upload_4.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	🗑️ 📄
6780972-3861-48c1-9c25-45e94b20a8b	VNF_test_upload_6.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	🗑️ 📄
20cab48-062c-4079-ad10-585ae0c6d68	VNF_test_upload_10.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	🗑️ 📄
a4236e37ef49-4609-b8ac-9c9678031c1d	simple_vnf.zip	SPAIN_STONC	READY	🗑️ 📄

Figure 18: Re-deploy VNF request status

A.2.4. Update VNF List

- Finally, the “Update List” button in Figure 19 can be used to force the update of the VNF list.

Filename	Owner	Last updated	Actions
VNF_test_upload_1.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	15.Oct.2020	🗑️ 📄
VNF_test_upload_2.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	15.Oct.2020	🗑️ 📄
VNF_test_upload_3.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	15.Oct.2020	🗑️ 📄
VNF_test_upload_4.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	19.Oct.2020	🗑️ 📄
VNF_test_upload_5.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	20.Oct.2020	🗑️ 📄
VNF_test_upload_10.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	28.Oct.2020	🗑️ 📄
simple_vnf.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	15.Dec.2020	🗑️ 📄

Figure 19: Update VNF List

A.3. DESIGN OF BLUEPRINTS AND NETWORK SERVICE DESCRIPTORS (NSDs)

- To design an experiment on the platform, initially, experiment developers have to prepare three types of blueprints, i.e., Vertical Service Blueprints (VSB), Context Blueprints (CtxBs), and Test Case Blueprints (TCB) (see 5G-EVE D4.4 D4.6 [2] for more information). If you are an experiment developer, the number of context blueprints depends on the number of contexts you want to consider in your experiment. For example, in the simplest use-case, we are considering one type of context, i.e., delay, and as a result, we have only one CtxB.
- For these blueprints (i.e., VSB, CtxBs and TCBs), the corresponding blueprint fields and the meaning have been defined in (see 5G-EVE D4.4 D4.6 [1][2] for more information).
- In summary, the VSB contains your vertical service components, virtual links and their interconnections.
- Whereas the CtxB contains the different network impairments, you want to apply to your vertical service. The 5G EVE platform provides two types of Context Blueprints, i.e., PASS_THROUGH and CONNECT (see 5G-EVE D4.3 [6], D4.4 [1], D4.6 [2] for more information). Before designing your CtxB, please ensure that you are familiar with each type of CtxB since this will affect how the composed NSD will be generated.
- And finally, the TCB contains the different actions/tests that are to be carried out on the vertical service. A detailed description of the TCB parameters is provided in section A.4.2.2.
- The 5G EVE platform provides a fourth type of blueprint called the Experiment Blueprint (ExpB); however, for this blueprint, the platform provides a wizard, so you don't need to design it beforehand. More details about this blueprint can be found in section A.4.3.
- The VSB, CtxB and ExpB should all have a corresponding NSD.
- The 5G EVE platform only accepts descriptors (i.e., blueprints and NSDs) in the “*JSON*” format.
- To assist in the design of Blueprints and the generation of NSDs, the 5G EVE portal provides the “Blueprint and NSD support tool”; in the subsequent sections, this tool will be discussed further.

A.3.1. Blueprint and NSD Support tool

- This tool can assist in the design of blueprints and the generation of the corresponding NSDs. To be able to use this tool to generate your NSDs reliably, please ensure to have the following in mind when designing your blueprints:
 - i) When preparing the blueprints, the atomic components' component id should correspond to the UUID of the VNF inside your VNFD descriptor file. This value of the component id will be translated into the VNFD id inside the NSD.
 - ii) Ensure that the endpoints defined in the blueprints correspond to the connection points defined in the VNFD file. The blueprint's endpoint names will be translated into the VNFD service access and connection points depending on the nomenclature used with the blueprints' endpoints. The connection points containing "sap" anywhere within the name will be translated into service access points (saps); it doesn't matter if it's lower-case or uppercase.
 - iii) Ensure to attach a service access point to every virtual link where you need a mapping to an existing network in your data centre. Depending on whether the service access point has been defined as a management sap or not, this will determine which existing network your VNF will be attached to during the network service instantiation.
 - iv) Moreover, when defining your endpoints, be careful about the "ranConnection: true/false" property because this will determine how your VNFs will be connected in the composed NSD. The endpoint with this property set to true should be a connection point that is reachable from the RAN and vice-versa. In particular, the algorithm will place the context(s) as close as possible to the RAN endpoint.

Therefore, it is important that at least one "sap" endpoint has the "ranConnection: true" inside the VSB because the algorithm will match it with the SapDescriptor in the NSD.

- v) The VSB virtual link attached to this endpoint with "ranConnection: true" will be added to the CtxB and the other private virtual link in the CtxB will be used to connect the CtxB to the VSB component.
 - vi) Finally, when designing the CtxBs, care should be given to the value of the “compositionStrategy” parameter, since this will determine the type of CtxB you are using in your vertical service when composing the NSD.
- With those few pointers in mind, we can go ahead to use the tool to assist in the blueprints design and the generation of the corresponding NSDs.
 - To use the tool, go to the portal homepage page shown in Figure 20 and select the “Design Experiment” tab.

Figure 20: 5G EVE portal home page

- Upon clicking on this section, you will be presented with the page similar to Figure 21.

Figure 21: Design Experiments page

- To use the tool, click on the “Support Tools list” section as indicated in Figure 21.
- On clicking, you will be presented with a page similar to Figure 22.

Figure 22: Support tools page

- The tool provides four main functionalities:
 - i) Blueprint and NSD Schemas (indicated as “Schemas” in Figure 22);
 - ii) NSD generation (referred to as “Generate NSD” in Figure 22);
 - iii) NSD composition (referred to as “Composer” in Figure 22);
 - iv) Blueprint and NSD validation (indicated as “Validation” in Figure 22).
- In the following sections, we will discuss how to use each of the above functionalities to assist in the design your blueprints and generation of the network service descriptors on the platform.

A.3.1.1. Blueprint and NSD Schemas

- This tool contains the schemas for the different blueprints i.e., VSB, CtxB, TCB & ExpB and network service descriptors used on the platform.
- For each blueprint and NSD, you can download the corresponding schema and follow the specified format when designing your descriptors.
- For example, when designing the vertical service blueprint (VSB), you can download the equivalent schema as indicated in Figure 23.

Figure 23: VSB Schema download

- The same procedure can be followed for all the other blueprints and network service descriptors.
- An example of a VSB blueprint following this schema with an explanation of the different fields is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/VSB/vsb_simple.yaml
- The json equivalent of the VSB is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/VSB/vsb_simple.json

- The CtxB for this simple use case following the available CtxB schema is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/tree/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/CtxB/ctxb_simple.yaml
- The json equivalent of the CtxB is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/tree/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/CtxB/ctxb_simple.json
- The TCB for this simple use case following the available TCB schema is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/TCB/Simple_UC_TCB.yaml
- The json equivalent of the TCB is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/TCB/Simple_UC_TCB.json

A.3.1.2. NSD Generation

- This tool can be used to generate NSDs corresponding to the blueprints designed in section A.3.1.1 above.
- To use this tool, go to the “Generate NSD” tab (step 1) and click on the “Choose file” button (step 2) to upload the blueprint (json format as it is presented in step 3) as indicated in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Generate NSD tool

- Finally, click on the “Download” button (step 4) to download the generated NSD and save it with a suitable filename. The generated NSD corresponding to the VSB presented in section A.3.1.1 above can be accessed at: https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/VSB/vsb_simple_nsd.json.
- The generated NSD corresponding to the CtxB presented in section A.3.1.1 above can be accessed at: https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/CtxB/ctxb_simple_nsd.json.

A.3.1.3. NSD Composition

- This tool referred to as “Composer” on the portal is used to combine the generated NSDs for the VSB and CtxBs from section A.3.1.2 to form a single “Composite NSD” that will be the actual NSD deployed by the platform.
- This “Composite NSD” is the NSD associated with the ExpB.

- To generate this “Composite NSD”, we follow the following steps:

Figure 25: NSD Composer tool

- First, upload the VSB (indicated as stage 1 in Figure 25).
- Next upload the corresponding NSD generated from section A.3.1.2 (indicated as stage 2 in Figure 25).
- Thirdly, upload the CtxB for your use case (indicated as stage 3 in Figure 25).
- Subsequently, upload the corresponding CtxB NSD (indicated as stage 4 in Figure 25).

Figure 26: Composed NSD download

- Next, if you select the “Add Details” box (indicated as stage 5 in Figure 26), then the tool provides you with a graphical representation of the composed NSD. You can use this graph to confirm that the NSD composition is in line with what you were expecting and make the necessary changes if needed.
 - Finally, by clicking on the “Download” button (indicated as stage 6 in Figure 26), you can download the composed NSD. This composed NSD is a zip folder with the composed NSD and a graphical representation of the composed NSD (“png format”). Save this composed NSD with a suitable file name.
- It is important to note that the “NSD Composition” tool will always place the experiment contexts as close as possible to the RAN. Therefore, if your experiment requires a more complex configuration, then in that case, by using the NSD schema provided in Section A.3.1.1, you can design your own Composite NSD.

A.3.1.4. Blueprint and NSD descriptors validation

- This tool can be used to validate all your blueprints and NSDs before uploading them to the portal.
- To verify any of the blueprints and NSDs, select the applicable schema depending on the blueprint or NSD you need to validate using the “arrow” button as illustrated in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Validate blueprints and NSDs

- For example, to validate that your VSB is correct, the first step is to select the “Vertical Service Blueprint Schema”, followed by uploading your VSB file. This process is illustrated in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Blueprints and NSD descriptors validation

- If your blueprint/NSD has no issues, then you will see the “validation SUCCESS” notification at the bottom of the page as indicated by step (3) in Figure 28. Otherwise, if your blueprint/NSD has any issues, then you will be given more details about the error sources.

A.3.2. Design of Multi-site Experiments’ Descriptors

- For the multi-site experiments, the experiment developers need to design the VSBs, CtxBs, and the corresponding NSDs for each of the sites included in the multi-site experiment. To design the blueprints and the NSDs, follow the steps mentioned in section A.3.1 above.
- Next, this is followed by the design of the inter-site VSB and the corresponding NSD. Accordingly, in the proceeding sections, we will discuss how to design the multi-site composite VSB and NSD.

A.3.2.1. Design of the Multi-site composite vertical service blueprint

- The multi-site VSB (sometimes referred to as the composite VSB) is the blueprint that encompasses all the VSBs for the constituent single sites involved in the multi-site experiment. Besides, this composite VSB can contain features related to the connectivity between the sites associated with the multi-site experiment.
- The features of this composite VSB are given in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Multi-site composite VSB

Field	Type	Items properties	Description
interSite	Boolean	N/A	Set to “true” for inter-site experiments
version	String	N/A	Composite VSB version number
name	String	N/A	Composite VSB name
description	String	N/A	Brief description of the multi-site experiment
parameters	Array	parameterId	Composite VSB parameter Id
		parameterName	Composite VSB parameter name
		parameterType	Composite VSB parameter type
		parameterDescription	Composite VSB parameter description
		applicabilityField	Field where this VSB parameter is used
atomicComponents	Array (Add an atomic component from each of the VSBs composing your composite VSB)	componentId	Atomic component Id for a constituent VSB (i.e., the single site VSB)
		serversNumber	The number of servers/VMs composing the atomic component
		compatibleSite	The compatible site for the constituent VSB
		Type	Type of atomic component, default is “SERVICE”
		associatedVsbId	The Id of the constituent VSB
applicationMetrics	Array	--	Composite VSB application metrics, data structure similar to the single-site VSB application metrics
endPoints	Array	--	Composite VSB endpoints, data structure similar to the single-site VSB end points
connectivityServices	Array	--	Composite VSB connectivity services, data structure similar to the single-site VSB connectivity services field.

compatibleSites	Array	--	A list of all the 5G EVE sites involved in this multi-site experiment. Valid values are: - ITALY_TURIN, SPAIN_5TONIC, FRANCE_PARIS, FRANCE_NICE, FRANCE_RENNES, GREECE_ATHENS
-----------------	-------	----	---

- An example of a simple composite VSB is given in Figure 29.

```

1 ---
2 interSite: true
3 version: '1.6'
4 name: Composite testing Service enhanced without radio_metrics
5 description: Composite VSB
6 parameters:
7 - parameterId: No_Of_UEs_Spain
8   parameterName: Number of User Equipments
9   parameterType: number
10  parameterDescription: Number of web users_Spain
11  (Mandatory)
12  applicabilityField: Simple Use Case
13 - parameterId: No_Of_UEs_Italy
14   parameterName: Number of User Equipments
15   parameterType: number
16   parameterDescription: Number of web users_Italy
17   (Mandatory)
18   applicabilityField: Simple Use Case
19 atomicComponents:
20 - componentId: "apache"
21   serversNumber: 1
22   compatibleSite: SPAIN_5TONIC
23   type: SERVICE
24   associatedVsbId: '211'
25 - componentId: tracker_turin
26   serversNumber: 1
27   associatedVsbId: '260'
28   compatibleSite: ITALY_TURIN
29   type: SERVICE
30 applicationMetrics: []
31 endPoints:
32 - endPointId: cp_tracker_ext_in_composite
33   external: true
34   management: false
35   ranConnection: true
36 connectivityServices:
37 - endPointIds:
38   - cp_tracker_ext_in_composite
39   management: true
40   external: true
41   name: tracker_ext
42 compatibleSites:
43 - SPAIN_5TONIC
44 - ITALY_TURIN

```

Figure 29: Simple Multi-site UC composite VSB

A.3.2.2. Design of the Multi-site composite NSD

- After designing the composite VSB for the multi-site experiment, we need to design the corresponding composite NSD.
- The features of the multi-site composite NSD are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Multi-site Composite NSD

Field	Type	Item properties	Item properties II	Description	
nsdIdentifier	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD unique identifier	
designer	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD designer	
version	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD version	
nsdName	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD name	
nsdInvariantId	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD Invariant Id	
nestedNsdId	Array	String	N/A	List of the nested NSD Ids comprising this composite NSD	
nsDf	Array	nsDfId	N/A	Specify the ID for the composite NS deployment flavour	
		flavourKey	N/A	Specify the key for the composite NS deployment flavour	
		This process is repeated for each possible NS instantiation level for the composite NSD			
		nsInstantiationLevel	nsLevelId		Specify the composite NS instantiation level Id.
			description		Add a description for the composite NS instantiation level.
			nsToLevelMapping : nsProfileId numberOfInstances		Specify the NS profile id for each of the nested NSDs. This NsProfileId should be the same as that specified inside the nested NSDs.
		defaultNsInstantiationLevelId	N/A		In case more than one NS instantiation level has been defined, specify the default instantiation level Id.
		For each of the nsProfileIds specified above, provide the following details			
		nsProfile	nsProfileId		Same as the one specified under the nsInstantiationLevel filed
			nsdId		The id of the nested NSD with the specified nsProfileId
nsDfId			The nested NSD Deployment flavour Id		

			nsInstantiationLevelId	The nested NSD Instantiation Level Id
			minNumberOfInstances	The minimum number of the nested NSD instances to launch
			maxNumberOfInstances	The maximum number of the nested NSD instances to launch

- An example of a multi-site composite NSD for the simple use case is provided in Figure 30.

```

1  ---
2  nsdIdentifier: compositeNSD_metrics_v1
3  designer: NXW & UC3M
4  version: '1.0'
5  nsdName: compositeNSDName_metrics_v1
6  nsdInvariantId: compositeNSDInvariantId_v1
7  nestedNsdId:
8  - vsbNestedNSD_metrics
9  - vsbNestedNSD2_metrics
10 nsDf:
11 - nsDfId: compositeNSD_df
12   flavourKey: compositeNSD_df
13   nsInstantiationLevel:
14   - nsLevelId: compositeNSD_il_small
15     description: compositeNSD small instantiation level
16     nsToLevelMapping:
17     - nsProfileId: vsbNestedNSD_profile_small
18       numberOfInstances: 1
19     - nsProfileId: vsbNestedNSD2_profile_small
20       numberOfInstances: 1
21   defaultNsInstantiationLevelId: compositeNSD_il_small
22   nsProfile:
23   - nsProfileId: vsbNestedNSD_profile_small
24     nsdId: vsbNestedNSD_metrics
25     nsDfId: vsb_apache_simple_df
26     nsInstantiationLevelId: vsb_apache_simple_il_default
27     minNumberOfInstances: 1
28     maxNumberOfInstances: 1
29   - nsProfileId: vsbNestedNSD2_profile_small
30     nsdId: vsbNestedNSD2_metrics
31     nsDfId: nestedNSD_df
32     nsInstantiationLevelId: nestedNSD_il_small
33     minNumberOfInstances: 1
34     maxNumberOfInstances: 1
35 security:
36   signature: SIGNATURE
37   algorithm: ALGORITHM
38   certificate: CERTIFICATE
39

```

Figure 30: Simple multi-site UC composite NSD

A.4. EXPERIMENT DESIGN USING THE 5G EVE PORTAL

- After an experiment developer has designed the corresponding blueprints and generated the corresponding NSDs, experimenters can start designing their experiments.
- If you are an experimenter, to start designing your experiment, go to portal home page and select the “Design Experiments” tab as shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: 5G EVE Portal Welcome Page

- Click on the Design Experiment icon, and you will be led to the design experiment page which looks similar to Figure 32.

Figure 32: 5G EVE Portal Experiment Design Page

- Once you are on the design experiment page, you will have access to all the different descriptors (i.e., blueprints, NSDs and VNFDs) available on the platform.
- And next, we shall proceed to upload our newly designed descriptors to the platform. So, go ahead and click on the “Blueprints” tab as indicated in Figure 32.

A.4.1. Uploading the Vertical Service Blueprint

- We are going to begin with the vertical service blueprints, and we will keep repeating the same steps for all the other blueprints.
- So, go ahead and click on the Vertical Service under the Blueprints section and you will be re-directed to a page similar to Figure 33.

Figure 33: 5G EVE Portal Vertical Service Blueprints Design Page

- As you can see, we have three tasks to perform here: Upload Blueprint, Upload NSDs and Create Translation Rules (indicated as step (2) in Figure 33).
- Beginning with task 1, upload the vertical service blueprint (VSB) from section A.3.
- Once you are done uploading the VSB, then click on the next button.
- Next, we move on to task 2 to upload the NSDs. As stated in section A.3 above, every VSB has a corresponding NSD, so go ahead and upload the NSD in json format (from section A.3) corresponding to your VSB. Once done, click the next button.
- Next, you will be directed to the create translation rules task; by this stage the portal would have already read the id and version of your uploaded NSD and they will be auto filled by the portal. Please refer to Figure 34 for more information.
- So, your only task is to select the Network Service (NS) Deployment Flavor id and Instantiation Level id that you want to use in this particular experiment.
- All the available NS Deployment Flavors and Instantiation Levels inside your NSD will be presented to you, and you just must select using the “arrow” button the right combination of Deployment Flavor and Instantiation Level ids that you want to use.
- The next field is the parameters section, for this field the 5G EVE portal will have already read the “parameters” section of your VSB. Thereafter, the portal will present you with your VSB parameters, so that you can select the range of each VSB parameter that you want to use in your experiment.
- If your VSB has more than one parameter, then click on the “+” icon inside to add more parameters.

Figure 34: 5G EVE Portal VSB Translation Rules

- Once you are done filling in and selecting all the required parameters, then you can go ahead and click the “submit” button.

A.4.1.1. Verification of the VSB submission

- After clicking the “submit” button, if your submission was successful then you will be presented with a message with the “**SUCCESS**” keyword in the body response.
- Otherwise, if your submission failed then you will be presented with an error response message with the “**FAILED**” keyword in the body response.
- In case your submission fails, then please refer to section 0 for some troubleshooting tips.
- Once the submission is successful, we can view our uploaded blueprint by clicking on the “view” tab as shown in Figure 35.

Id	Name	Version	Description	Configurable Parameters
21	ARES2T Tracker service	1.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Tracker service using 5G network to collect mobility data user devices.	~ Number of tracked devices
115	ASTI AGV control and automation	1.0	Blueprint for AGVs using 5G network for Automation and Control purposes	~ Number of AGVs

Figure 35: 5G EVE View Uploaded Blueprint

- As we can see in Figure 35, the submission was successful hence the ASTI AGV VSB is also listed.
- In order to view our uploaded blueprint, click on the eye icon as shown in Figure 35.
- Clicking on the eye icon, our blueprint looks as shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36: 5G EVE Portal Uploaded VSB View

NOTE:

- Sometimes, it’s possible that your upload was successful however when you click on the eye icon, you are not able to view your blueprint.
- In that case, please refer to section 0 for some trouble-shooting tips.
- Your VSB upload is only considered successful if you can view the VSB using the eye icon in the “view” tab.

A.4.2. Uploading of the Context Blueprints

- Go back to the blueprints section, and this time, select the Execution context as shown in Figure 37.
- The procedure to upload the execution context blueprints is the same as the procedure to upload the vertical service blueprints (section A.4.1), as shown in Figure 37.
- The only difference is that now you will be uploading the context blueprints from section A.3 with the corresponding NSDs instead of VSBs.

Figure 37: 5G EVE Execution Context Blueprints Upload

- Please remember that you have to upload all the context blueprints from section A.3 and the corresponding NSDs you expect to use in your experiment.
- Please refer to section A.4.1 above and apply the same principles to the context NSDs in your experiment to help understand the translation rules,
- Once done, please click the “submit” button.

A.4.2.1. Verification of the Execution Context Blueprints submission

- After clicking the “submit” button, if your submission was successful, then you will be presented with a message with the “**SUCCESS**” keyword in the body response.
- Otherwise, if your submission failed, then you will be presented with an error response message with the “**FAILED**” keyword in the body response.
- In case your submission fails, then please refer to section 0 for some troubleshooting tips.
- To check that all the relevant context blueprints for your experiment have been successfully uploaded, please click on the “view” tab of your execution context blueprints. As we can see from the “view” tab, the two context blueprints were uploaded successfully for this use case, as shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38: 5G EVE Execution Context Blueprints view

- To verify that our context blueprints were successfully onboarded, we need to click on the “eye” icon for each of the context blueprints as shown in Figure 38.
- If the upload was successful, you will be able to view each of your uploaded context blueprints. In our case, the two contexts are illustrated in Figure 39 and Figure 40.

Figure 39: 5G EVE ASTI Use-case delay context blueprint view

Figure 40: 5G EVE ASTI Use-case Background traffic context blueprint view

- In case you can't view one or more of your context blueprints, please refer to section 0 of this document for some troubleshooting tips.
- Once we are done uploading and verifying the uploaded context blueprints, we are ready to start on the test case blueprints.

A.4.2.2. Uploading of the Test Case Blueprints

- Go back to the blueprints section and this time, select “Test Case” blueprints, and you will be presented with a page similar to Figure 41.

Figure 41: 5G EVE Portal Test Case Blueprint Onboarding

- The platform provides two options for uploading the TCB i.e., Direct TCB Upload (indicated as step (2) in Figure 41) or Creating the TCB on the fly (indicated as step (3) in Figure 41).
- In the following sections, we are going to discuss the meaning of the different fields of the TCB and finally provide examples of TCBs based on the two options.

A.4.2.3. TCB parameters definition

- To begin with, let us try to understand what each of the test-case blueprint form parameters represent:

- The name, description and version parameters are compulsory. So, go ahead and fill them in.
- Just remember you can only have one combination of name and version for each test-case blueprint.
- So, let us focus on the highlighted parameters:
 - Label 1 - Configuration Script**
 - This parameter captures all the commands and/or scripts required to configure your vertical service to be ready to produce the application and/or infrastructure metrics.
 - Label 2 - Execution Script**
 - This parameter captures all the commands and/or scripts required to generate the application and/or infrastructure metrics for your vertical service test case.
 - Label 3 - Reset configuration Script**
 - This optional parameter captures all the commands and/or scripts required to clean/clear your vertical service environment after it has finished executing the test case.
 - Label 4 - User Parameters**
 - Here, we provide all the parameters needed to access our vertical service components (e.g., authentication) and run the test case (e.g., script arguments).
 - This can also include the user parameters required to access and run the context components.
 - Use the “+” icon to add more user parameters.
 - Label 5 - Infrastructure Parameters**
 - These are the parameters that should be provided by the 5G EVE platform to your test case for successful execution.
 - Examples include: VNF ip addresses, application metric topic id to publish the data too, so that it’s viewable in the 5G EVE monitoring and reporting tool.

- Once you are done filling in the test case blueprint (TCB) parameters, then you can submit your TCB by clicking on the “submit” button.

A.4.2.4. TCB Examples

- An example of a filled-in test case blueprint is given in Figure 42. More information can be found in D4.3 [6].

Switch to TCB upload via JSON file

Create Test Case

Simple_UC_TCB

5G EVE Simple use case TCB

1.0

EXECUTE_COMMAND vnf.be55660e-8961-11ea-bc55-0242ac130003.extcp.eth0.ipaddress \$\$userB:\$\$passwordB sudo /bin/bash /home/test/day2-configuration-only.sh \$\$metric.topic.requests

EXECUTE_COMMAND vnf.ef5fa76-895b-11ea-bc55-0242ac130003.extcp.eth0.ipaddress \$\$userB:\$\$passwordB sudo tc qdisc add dev ens4 root netem delay 10ms 5ms 25%; EXECUTE_COM

EXECUTE_COMMAND vnf.ef5fa76-895b-11ea-bc55-0242ac130003.extcp.eth0.ipaddress \$\$userB:\$\$passwordB sudo tc qdisc del dev ens4 root

User Parameters

Param 1 userB \$\$userB

Param 2 passwordB \$\$passwordB

Param 3 concurrent \$\$concurrent

Param 4 sleepTime \$\$sleepTime

Param 5 noOfRequests \$\$noOfRequests

Infrastructure Parameters

Param 1 \$\$metric.topic.requests_time

Param 2 vnf.ef5fa76-895b-11ea-bc55

Param 3 vnf.ef5fa76-895b-11ea-bc55

Param 4 vnf.be55660e-8961-11ea-bc55

Submit

Figure 42: 5G EVE Portal Simple_UseCase_TCB

- On the other hand, an example of a simple TCB that can be uploaded directly to the platform is available at https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/TCB/Simple_UC_TCB.json

A.4.2.5. Verification of the Test Case Blueprints submission

- After clicking on the “submit” button, if your submission was successful, you will be presented with a message with the “**SUCCESS**” keyword in the body response.
- Otherwise, if your submission failed, you will be presented with an error response message with the “**FAILED**” keyword in the body response.
- In case your submission fails, please refer to section 0 for some troubleshooting tips.
- To verify that your submission was successful, click of the “view” tab of the test case blueprints, and you will see your submitted TCB in the list. For our example, this is illustrated in Figure 43.

ID	Name	Version	Description	User Parameters	Individual Parameters
11	Apache Simple TCB	1.0	Apache Simple TCB	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
41	TCB SEOTTUR test case 1	1.0	Test case to run the SEOTTUR use case	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
54	Apache_TCB_v2	2.0	TCB Apache simple v2	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
71	Apache_TCB_v3	3.0	Apache_TCB_v3	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
80	test_casch	1.0	test_casch	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
100	TCB SEOTTUR test case 2	1.0	Test case to run the SEOTTUR use case 2	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
118	Apache_TCB_v4_v4	2.0	Apache_TCB_v4_v4	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
128	apache_vault_v4_v4_v2	2.0	apache_vault_v4_v4_v2	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
144	TCB SEOTTUR test case 31	3.1	Test case to run the SEOTTUR use case 31	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User
162	apache_tcb	1.0	TCB for the Simple Apache User Case	- parameter: \$ExperimentID - parameter: \$ExperimentName - user: \$User - user: \$User	- \$ExperimentID: \$ExperimentID - \$ExperimentName: \$ExperimentName - \$User: \$User - \$User: \$User

Figure 43: 5G EVE Simple_Usecase_TCB View

- Once we are done verifying the test case blueprints, then we are ready to move on to the Experiment blueprints.

A.4.3. Uploading of the Experiment Blueprints

- In order to design the Experiment Blueprint, go back to the “descriptors” section and select Experiment as shown in Figure 44.

Figure 44: 5G EVE Portal Experiment Blueprint Design

- The fields highlighted in red are compulsory.
- Proceed to fill in the id, name, version and optionally the description that you want to use for your experiment blueprint. Remember, you can only have one unique combination of the name and version.
- Once you are done filling in these fields, click “Next” to go to the VSB selection stage. An example of a filled-in experiment blueprint form is given in Figure 45.

The screenshot shows the 'Experiment Blueprints' interface in the 'Onboard' stage. The 'General Information' step is active, showing a progress bar with three steps: 1. General Information, 2. VSB Selection, and 3. CB Selection. Below the progress bar, the 'Experiment Blueprint' section contains four input fields: a hexadecimal ID (648d1427-163e-4893-9d68-c71a691b2283), a name (asti_agv_expb), a version (2.0), and a description (ASTI AGV experiment blueprint v2). At the bottom, the 'Blueprint Name' is displayed as 'asti_agv_expb' and a 'Next' button is visible.

Figure 45: 5GEVE Portal ASTI_UseCase Experiment Blueprint

- Click “Next” to move on to the VSB selection stage. In the VSB selection stage, using the “arrow” icon, select the site where you want to conduct the experiment, and thereafter, select the VSB that you want to use in that site. All your uploaded VSBs will be availed to you, and you can use the “arrow” icon to select the VSB that you want to use for this experiment. This process is illustrated further in Figure 46.

The screenshot shows the 'Experiment Blueprints' interface in the 'Onboard' stage. The 'VSB Selection' step is active, showing a progress bar with three steps: 1. General Information, 2. VSB Selection, and 3. CB Selection. Below the progress bar, there are two dropdown menus: 'Site' and 'VSB'. Below the dropdowns, the 'Blueprint Name' is displayed as 'asti_agv_expb', and there are labels for 'Selected Site:' and 'Selected VSB:'. At the bottom, there are 'Back' and 'Next' buttons.

Figure 46: 5G-EVE Portal VSB Selection

Figure 47: 5G-EVE Portal VSB Selection

- An example of a selected site and VSB for the ASTI Use-Case is given in Figure 47.
- Click “Next” to move on to the Context Blueprint selection process.
- At this point, all the compatible context blueprints related to your VSB are available to you, and you have to select the context blueprint that you want to use for your experiment, as demonstrated in Figure 48. In this case, we selected both the delay and background traffic context blueprints.

Figure 48: 5G-EVE ASTI_USeCase CtxB Selection

- Click “Next” to move on to the NSD Onboarding stage. At this point, you have to upload the **composite NSD** we prepared in section **A.3.1.3**.
- So, click on “Choose file”, and select your “composite NSD” file that encompasses both your VSB and CtxB NSDs. With reference to Figure 49, at point 2, you will be able to view your onboarded composite NSD.

Figure 49: 5G EVE ASTI Use_Case Composite NSD Uploading

- Click “Next” to move on to the translation rules step. You will be presented with a page similar to Figure 50.
- In the translation rules section, the id and version of the uploaded composite NSD will have already been read by the portal.
- Next using the “arrow” icon, select the Network Service (NS) Deployment flavor and NS Instantiation Level id that you want to use in your experiment.
- Next, fill in the range of the parameters listed in both your VSB and context blueprints. Click on the “+” icon to add more parameters.

Figure 50: 5G EVE Composite NSD Translation rules

- An example of the composite NSD translation rules for the ASTI use-case is shown in Figure 51. The “*number_of_AGVs*” parameter is listed inside the parameters section of the ASTI VSB, the “*incoming_traffic_load*” parameter is listed inside the parameters section of the ASTI delay context blueprint, whereas the “*bg_traffic_rate*” is listed inside the parameters section of the ASTI background traffic context blueprint.

Figure 51: 5G EVE ASTI Composite NSD Translation Rules.

- Once done filling in all the required values, click “Next” to move on to the Metrics & KPIs section.
- In the Metrics & KPIs section, you have two parts i.e., Metrics and KPIs as illustrated in Figure 52. To understand what each of the parameters in the Metrics and KPIs parts means, please refer to Table 4.
- The Metrics requested at this stage are the same metrics listed in your context blueprints under the “applicationMetrics” section. When in doubt, please refer to the values you put in that section of the context blueprint.

Figure 52: 5G EVE Experiment Blueprint Metrics & KPIs Section

Table 4: 5G EVE Metrics & KPIs parameters

Part 1- Metrics		
Parameter Type	Description	Comments
Metric Type	Type of the metric you want to measure	Current possible values [LOST_PKT, RECEIVED_PKT, SENT_PKT, LATENCY, BANDWIDTH]
Interval	The time interval by which you want to measure your metric	Depends on the metric you are considering
Collection Type	Metric collection method	Current possible values [CUMULATIVE, DELTA, GAUGE]
Metric Id	Id of your metric	uuid format
Graph Type	Type of Graph to use to display the metric	Current possible values [LINE, PIE, COUNTER, GAUGE]
Name	Name of the metric	
Unit	Standard SI Unit in which the metric is to be measured	For time-related metrics, this could be “s” for seconds and “ms” for milliseconds
<i>To add more metrics, please click on the “+” icon</i>		
Part 2 – KPIs		
Parameter Type	Description	Comments
Formula	Formula/Equation to compute your KPIs	In case your KPI is as a result of applying some sort of operation(s)/formula to the collected metrics. Otherwise, if your KPI is the same as the collected metric, then in that case just put the metric name as the formula.
Interval	Interval at which this KPI should be computed	Depends on the KPIs you are looking at
KPI Id	Id of your KPI	uuid format
Graph Type	Type of Graph to use to display the KPI	Current possible values [LINE, PIE, COUNTER, GAUGE]
Name	Name of the KPI	
Unit	Standard SI Unit of the KPI	For time related KPIs, this could be “s” for seconds and “ms” for milliseconds
Metric Ids	Ids of the metrics you want to consider for this KPI	Add all the metric ids of the metrics used for this KPI. These metrics should be related to the formula given above
<i>To add more metrics, please click on the “+” icon</i>		

- An example of a filled-in Metrics & KPIs section for the ASTI Use-Case is given in Figure 53.

Metric 1

Metric Type: LATENCY | Collection Type: 1 | GAUGE | Graph Type: LINE

asti_agv_latency | asti_agv_latency | ms

Metric 2

Metric Type: LOST_PKT | Collection Type: 1 | GAUGE | Graph Type: LINE

asti_agv_lost_pkts | asti_agv_lost_pkts | percentage

KPIs

KPI 1

asti_agv_latency | 1 | asti_agv_latency_kpi | Graph Type: LINE

asti_agv_latency_kpi | ms | asti_agv_latency

KPI 2

100 - (asti_agv_lost_pkts) | 1 | asti_agv_reliability_kpi | Graph Type: LINE

asti_agv_reliability_kpi | percentage | asti_agv_lost_pkts

Figure 53: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Metrics & KPIs

- Click “Next” to move on to the “Test Cases” section.
- In the “Test Cases” section, please select one of the test-case blueprints that you created earlier (in section A.4.2.2) as shown in Figure 54.

superusertest | Home | Blueprints | Descriptors | Back

Experiment Blueprints

View | Onboard

General Information | VSB Selection | CB Selection | NSD Onboarding | Translation Rules | Metrics & KPIs | **7 Test Cases**

description

ASTI delay test case

ASTI delay test case2

Blueprint Name: asti_agv_exp0

Selected Site: SIPM_STONC

Selected VSB: IT5

Selected Ctx: 98

Uploaded NSD: asti_agv_all_nsd.json

Metrics: ASTI_Traffic_delay

KPIs: latency

Selected TDC: 133

Back | Reset | Submit

Figure 54: 5G EVE ExpB Test Case Blueprint Selection

- Once done, please click on the “Submit” button to submit your completed experiment blueprint (ExpB) which contains your selected VSB, CtxB, TCB, composite NSD, KPIs and Infrastructure metrics.

A.4.3.1. Verification of the Experiment Blueprints submission

- After clicking the “submit” button, if your submission was successful, you will be presented with a message with the “**SUCCESS**” keyword in the body response.
- Otherwise, if your submission failed, you will be presented with an error response message with the “**FAILED**” keyword in the body response.
- In case your submission fails, please refer to section 0 for some troubleshooting tips.
- In order to verify that your Experiment Blueprint was uploaded successfully, please click on the “**view**” tab of the Experiment Blueprints section. This is illustrated in Figure 55.

Figure 55: 5G EVE Experiment Blueprints View

- As you can see from Figure 55, our experiment is listed however to confirm that the submission was successful then we have to click on the eye icon.
- Clicking on the eye icon, we can see that we are able to view our experiment blueprint as shown in Figure 56.

Figure 56: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Experiment Blueprint

- At this point, we are done with designing our experiment, hence we are ready to move on the next section i.e., Requesting an experiment.

A.4.4. MULTI-SITE COMPOSITE DESCRIPTORS DESIGN

- For multi-site experiments, the procedure for uploading the composite blueprints and NSDs is a little different.
- First of all, upload the VSBs for each constituent site involved in the multi-site experiment following the steps provided Section A.4.1; and thereafter, for each nested VSB upload, the experiment developer has to note down the Id as provided by the portal. An example of a nested VSB Id is indicated in Figure 57.

Id	Name	Version	Description	Configurable Parameters	
774	Gaming Use Case Nested_ns_ES_v3	3.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming Use Case_Spain_v3	- Number of players	
782	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming Use Case_Greece_v3	3.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming UC_v3	- Number of players	
790	Composite VSB for the Gaming multi-site UC_v3	3.0	Composite VSB for the Gaming multi-site UC_v3	- Number of players - Number of players	
862	Simple_VSB_with_Apache_02_03_diagnosis	6.0	Simple VSB – Apache instance and a delay generator	- Number of user equipments	
879	Gaming Use Case Nested_ns_ES_v4	4.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming Use Case_Spain_v4	- Number of players	
887	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming Use Case_Greece_v5	5.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming UC_v5	- Number of players	
895	Composite VSB for the Gaming multi-site UC_v4	4.0	Composite VSB for the Gaming multi-site UC_v4	- Number of players - Number of players - Number of players	

Figure 57: Composite VSB_Nested VSB Id

- Upon finishing the nested VSB uploads and noting down their Ids, go ahead and update the composite VSB to reflect these nested VSB Ids as illustrated in Figure 58.

```

1 ---
2 interSite: true
3 version: '1.6'
4 name: Composite testing Service enhanced without radio_metrics
5 description: Composite VSB
6 parameters:
7 - parameterId: No_Of_UEs_Spain
8   parameterName: Number of User Equipments
9   parameterType: number
10  parameterDescription: Number of web users_Spain
11  (Mandatory)
12  applicabilityField: Simple Use Case
13 - parameterId: No_Of_UEs_Italy
14   parameterName: Number of User Equipments
15   parameterType: number
16   parameterDescription: Number of web users_Italy
17   (Mandatory)
18   applicabilityField: Simple Use Case
19 atomicComponents:
20 - componentId: "apache"
21   serversNumber: 1
22   compatibleSite: SPAIN_STONIC
23   type: SERVICE
24   associatedVsbId: '211'
25 - componentId: tracker_turin
26   serversNumber: 1
27   associatedVsbId: '260'
28   compatibleSite: ITALY_TURIN
29   type: SERVICE
30 applicationMetrics: []
31 endPoints:
32 - endPointId: cp_tracker_ext_in_composite
33   external: true
34   management: false
35   ranConnection: true
36 connectivityServices:
37 - endPointIds:
38   - cp_tracker_ext_in_composite
39   management: true
40   external: true
41   name: tracker_ext
42 compatibleSites:
43 - SPAIN_STONIC
44 - ITALY_TURIN

```

Updated Nested VSB
Ids after uploading all
the nested VSBs to the
portal

Figure 58: Updating the Composite VSB before uploading

- After updating the composite VSB with the updated nested VSB Ids, go ahead and upload it to the platform following the steps presented in section A.4.1.
- Proceed to upload the composite TCB and create the Experiment blueprint following the steps presented in Sections A.4.2.2 and A.4.3, respectively.
- When done, proceed with the following sections to request, instantiate and execute your multi-site experiment.

A.5. 5G EVE PORTAL REQUEST EXPERIMENT

- In this section, we will cover the steps taken in order to request an experiment in the 5G EVE portal.
- Go back to the 5G EVE portal home page and this time, click on the “Request Experiments” tool as shown in Figure 59.

Figure 59: 5G EVE Portal Home Page

- After clicking on the “Request Experiments” section, you will be presented with a screen similar to the one shown in Figure 60.
- Inside the 5G EVE portal, you can request an experiment by using either the “**Experiment Descriptors create**” wizard or by using the “**Intent-based networking (IBN) experiment scheduling**” tool as illustrated in Figure 60.

Figure 60: 5G EVE Portal Request Experiments page

A.5.1. 5G EVE PORTAL CREATE EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTOR

- To request an experiment using the “Experiment Descriptors create” wizard, go ahead and click on the “*Experiment Descriptors Create*” icon. This wizard will guide you through the steps needed to create the various descriptors of your experiment i.e., Vertical Service, Context, Test-Case and Experiment Descriptors.
- Once inside the “*Experiment Descriptors Create*”, you will be presented with a form similar to Figure 61.
- So, go ahead and use the “arrow” icon to select the experiment blueprint associated to this experiment descriptor followed by the name and version.

Figure 61: 5G EVE Experiment Descriptor metadata page

- An example of the Experiment descriptor metadata for the ASTI use case that we have been using in this document is given in Figure 62.

Figure 62: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Experiment Descriptors Metadata

- Click “Next” to move on to the “VS Descriptors” section. The “VS Descriptors” page is displayed in Figure 63.

Figure 63: 5G EVE Vertical Service Descriptor page

- Inside the “*VS Descriptors*” section, please input the name and version you want to use for the Vertical Service Descriptor.
- The main difference between the Vertical Service Descriptor (VSD) and Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB) is that the VSD is the parameterized version of your VSB, i.e. inside the VSD, the actual values of the VSB parameters to be used in the experiment are provided.
- Inside the VSD, the VSB parameters are captured by the QoS parameters section. So, using the “arrow” icon, go ahead and select the VSB parameter to associate with your VSD.
- Next, we move on to the Slice Parameters selection. Please click on the “arrow” button, and you will be presented with the parameters shown in Table 5.

Table 5: 5G EVE VSD Slice Parameters Description

Slice Parameters		
Parameter	Possible Values	Description
Management_Type	Provider_Managed	This vertical service is to be managed by the 5G EVE system
	Tenant_Managed	This vertical service will be managed by the Vertical Service Provider
Slice_Service_Type	EMBB	Mobile Broadband use-cases
	URLLC	High bandwidth with ultra-low latency applications
	M_IOT	Massive Internet-of-devices

- Select the Management_Type and Slice_Service_Type that correspond to your use-case.
- Finally, check public if your experiment is publicly available to every user of the 5G EVE platform. Please refer to Figure 64 for the VSD of the ASTI use-case that we have been using in this document.

Figure 64: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case VSD parameters

- Click “Next” to move on to the “KPIs” section. As you can in Figure 65, the KPI that we added in the ASTI Experiment blueprint has already been selected for us. In this example, this KPI is ASTI_latency.

Figure 65: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case ExpD KPI

- Click “Next” to move on to the “Context Details” section. As you can see in Figure 66, the context associated with our Experiment blueprint has also already been selected for us.

Figure 66: 5G EVE ASTI ExpD Delay_Context

- By clicking on the “ASTI traffic Delay Generator Service”, the parameter(s) associated with your delay context blueprint will be presented to you and you have to select the actual value(s) of the parameter(s) that you want to use in this experiment. This is illustrated in Figure 67.

Figure 67: 5G EVE ASTI ExpD Delay_Context Parameter

- Click “Next” to go to the “*Test Cases Configuration*” section. As you can in Figure 68, our “ASTI delay test case” associated with this experiment blueprint is already available to us. So, go ahead and click on the “arrow” button to select our test case parameter values.

Figure 68: 5G EVE ExpD Test Cases Configuration

- For the ASTI Use-Case, the test cases configuration parameter(s) are detailed in Figure 69.

Figure 69: 5G EVE ASTI ExpD Delay Test Case Parameters

- Once done, click on the “Submit” button to submit your Experiment Descriptor.

A.5.1. Verification of the Experiment Descriptor submission

- In order to verify that your Experiment Descriptor was uploaded successfully, please click on the “view” tab of the Experiment Descriptors section. This is illustrated in Figure 70.

Figure 70: 5G EVE Experiment Descriptors View

- As you can see from Figure 70, our experiment is listed. However, to confirm that the submission was successful, we have to click on the eye icon.
- Clicking on the eye icon, we can see that we are able to view our descriptors as shown in Figure 71.

Figure 71: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Experiment Descriptor Details

- In case you can't view one or more of your Experiment Descriptor, please refer to section **0** for some trouble-shooting tips.
- Now we are ready to schedule our experiment with the 5G EVE portal.

A.6. 5G EVE INTENT-BASED NETWORKING (IBN) EXPERIMENT SCHEDULING TOOL

- To request an experiment using the IBN experiment scheduling tool, go ahead and click on the “Intent Declaration” icon as shown in Figure 72.

Figure 72: 5G EVE Request Experiment using The IBN Tool

- The IBN tool offers two modes of operation: intent-based selection and the guided selection.
- The intent-based section enables the user to write his intent using natural language, defining the desired service, sites, and relevant parameters to customize an experiment.
- The guided selection consists of a step-by-step wizard to set up and schedule the desired experiment.
- After clicking on the “Intent Declaration” icon, a login page as shown in Figure 73, appears as the user must enter his 5G-EVE credentials to authenticate using the Role-Based Access Control Interface (RBAC).

Figure 73: 5G EVE IBN RBAC page

- A logout button appears at the upper right corner to quickly log out and terminate the active session.
- After RBAC authorizes the user, the intent-based and guided selection tools become available.

A.6.1. Intent based selection

In this mode, the user is asked to fill in the blank field with his intent. An intent can contain the following ones:

- Information from the desired experiment's description, so that the most fitting experiment blueprint is found (i.e., experiment with ares2t);

- Information about the desired site following the keyword "in" (i.e., in Italy, in Turin, in Greece etc.);
- Information about the experiment date that the user desires in the dd/mm/yyyy format (i.e., 26/06/2020);
- Information about the experiment start time in the hh:mm 24h format (i.e., 16:45);
- Values for the service and context parameters using the "#" sign followed by the value;
- Information about the experiment duration in minutes using the "#" sign followed by the duration and the "duration" keyword (i.e., #30 duration).

Table 6: 5G EVE intent-based selection parameters

5G EVE Intent Parameters	Possible values
Experiment use-case	ares2t, asti, orange_v360, polito_smartcity and wings_utilities
5G EVE site	Turin (Italy), 5TONIC(Spain), Athens (Greece), Paris (France), Nice (France), Rennes (France)
Date(dd/mm/yyyy)	16/06/2020
Time (hh:mm 24h format)	18:50
vsb and context parameters (begin with '#')	#5 devices (vsb parameter) and #10 load (ctxb parameter)
Experiment duration in minutes (begin with '#')	#40 duration

- Therefore, a full intent that captures all these parameters can be as follows:
"experiment with ares2t in Turin on 16/06/2020 and time 18:50 with #5 devices and #10 load and #20 delay and #40 duration"
- This is illustrated further in Figure 74.

Figure 74: 5G EVE Intent Expression

- The input is analysed, and the optimal service and experiment blueprint pair is shown to the user along with the extracted site similar to Figure 75.

Please fill in the missing parameters:

Site: ITALY_TURIN
 Service blueprint: ARES2T Tracker service
 Experiment blueprint: ARES2T tracking experiment

[Retry](#) [Guided](#)

[ARES2T Tracker service] - service parameters

Number of tracked devices:

[Delay Generator] - context parameters

Incoming Traffic Load:

[TCB Ares2T Tracking with delay] - test case parameters

delay:

delay variance:

consecutive delay dependency percentage:

Experiment descriptor details

Name:

Experiment details

Date

Day: Month: Year:

Time

Hour: Minute:

Duration

Minutes:

[Submit](#)
1 field(s) left

Figure 75: 5G EVE Intent based tool-Experiment blueprint and service parameters selection

- All the parameters and experiment date/time/duration values that were recovered from the user's input are displayed in case the user wants to edit any value.
- It is important to note that the description field of each experiment blueprint that is onboarded at the Catalogue is evaluated and the one that is more correlated with the user intent is chosen.
- If every field has the desired value, the user submits the form.
- An experiment descriptor is created with all the information and is onboarded at the Portal Catalogue.
- Finally, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) is notified about the desired experiment details and the scheduling takes place.

A.6.2. Guided Selection

- In this section, the user follows a step-by-step approach accompanied with useful messages in order to configure an experiment.
- Initially, the user selects the desired site(s) to run an experiment as shown in Figure 76.

Figure 76: 5G EVE Intent Guided selection-select site

- The services that are supported in the selected site are shown in Figure 77 and the user chooses the suitable one.

Figure 77: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site- Available Services

- The experiments that contain the selected service are shown and the desired one must be chosen as illustrated in Figure 78.

Figure 78: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site- select desired experiment

- All the vertical service and context blueprint parameters are displayed, and the user is asked to fill in the desired values as shown in Figure 79.

Figure 79: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site- Select VSB and CtxB parameters

- All the test case parameters are displayed, per test case, and the user is asked to fill in the desired values as shown in Figure 80.
- If the user desires to exclude a test case, he/she may put the value "-" to a parameter of this test case.

Figure 80: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site- select test case parameters

- Finally, the date/time/duration parameters of the experiment are asked and if the input is valid the user can submit the form as shown in Figure 81.

Figure 81: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site-schedule experiment using the intent-based tool

- Once again, an experiment descriptor is created with all the information and is onboarded at the Portal Catalogue and the Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) is notified about the desired experiment details and the scheduling takes place.

A.7. 5G EVE PORTAL SCHEDULE EXPERIMENT

- This option is only required for those who used the Experiment Descriptors create wizard to create their descriptors.
- For those who used the intent tool, the experiment was already scheduled using the intent tool when you selected the time, date and duration of your experiment.
- To schedule an experiment, click on the “*New Experiment Schedule*” section as shown in Figure 82.

Figure 82: 5G EVE Request Experiments page

- On clicking the “*New Experiment Schedule*”, you are directed to the “*Schedule a New Experiment*” page shown in Figure 83.

Figure 83: 5G EVE Schedule a New Experiment

- To schedule an experiment, input the experiment’s name and then select the Experiment Descriptor’s name that you want to use by using the “arrow” icon.
- Thereafter, select the 5G EVE “*target site*” where you want to carry out your experiment. This parameter corresponds to the value of the “*compatibleSites*” parameter inside the VSB.
- Then, please select the start and end date of your experiment.
- An example of a scheduled experiment for the ASTI Use-Case is illustrated in Figure 84.

The screenshot shows the '5G EVE Portal' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the user 'superusertest', a home icon, 'Descriptors', and a back arrow. Below this, the page title is 'Schedule a New Experiment'. The main form area contains several input fields: a text box with 'astl_delay_test_experiment', a dropdown menu for 'Experiment Descriptor' set to 'ASTI AGV Experiment Blueprint', and another dropdown menu for 'Target Site' set to 'SPAIN_STONIC'. Below these are two date pickers, one showing '4/17/2020' and the other '4/24/2020'. At the bottom of the form is a green 'Submit' button.

Figure 84: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Scheduled Experiment

- Finally, click the “Submit” button to schedule an experiment.

A.8. MANAGE EXPERIMENT

- To view your scheduled experiment, go back to the 5G EVE home page.
- Then click on the “*Manage experiment*” section as shown in Figure 85.

Figure 85: 5G EVE Manage Experiment Section

- Clicking on the “*Manage Experiment*” section, you will see your scheduled experiment as shown in Figure 86.

Figure 86: 5G EVE Experiment List

- At this stage, the site managers of the selected 5G EVE site will receive a ticket with your experiment request.
- If all the required experiment resources are available at the selected 5G EVE site, and the timeline is not an issue, then your experiment will be accepted, otherwise it will be rejected with a reason for the rejection.
- Going forward, to be able to test the experiment execution process of the portal, we are going to use a simpler use case (client - webserver service) because the VNFs needed to execute the ASTI use case were not ready at the time of writing this user manual.

- Once an experiment is accepted by the site manager of the selected 5G EVE site, then the experiment status inside the 5G EVE portal will change from “*SCHEDULING*” to “*ACCEPTED*” as shown in Figure 87.

The screenshot shows the 'Experiments' section of the 5G EVE portal. It features a table with columns for Id, Descriptor Id, Sites, Status, and Execution Status. A blue arrow points to the 'ACCEPTED' status of the second experiment.

Id	Descriptor Id	Sites	Status	Execution Status
1	Test	SPAIN_STONIC	INSTANTIATED	
3	apache_exp_27_05	SPAIN_STONIC	ACCEPTED	

Figure 87: 5G EVE Experiment Accepted

- After an experiment is accepted on the portal, you have to wait for the experiment status to change to “*READY*” before you can be able to execute your experiment on the platform. In some vertical services, the site managers might need to do some manual configurations to prepare the 5G EVE sites for the experiment execution.
- Once the experiment status changes to ready, as shown in Figure 88. Then, we are prepared to execute our experiment on the platform.

The screenshot shows the 'Experiments' section of the 5G EVE portal. It features a table with columns for Id, Descriptor Id, Sites, Status, and Execution Status. A blue arrow points to the 'READY' status of the second experiment.

Id	Descriptor Id	Sites	Status	Execution Status
1	Test	SPAIN_STONIC	INSTANTIATED	
3	apache_exp_27_05	SPAIN_STONIC	READY	

Figure 88: 5G EVE Experiment Ready

A.9. DEPLOY AND EXECUTE EXPERIMENT

- To execute an experiment on the 5G EVE platform, click on the icon indicated by the blue arrow in Figure 89.
- Upon clicking on that icon, you will be presented with a screen similar to Figure 89. Select “DEPLOY” and after click “Submit” to execute your experiment.

Figure 89: 5G EVE Execute an Experiment

- On submission, the experiment will start executing on the portal, and the experiment status will change to “*INSTANTIATING*” as indicated in Figure 90.

Figure 90: 5G EVE Experiment Instantiating

- Once the platform completes instantiating the experiment, the experiment status will change to “*INSTANTIATED*” as shown in Figure 91 or “*FAILED*” in case the instantiation has failed for whatever reason.

Figure 91: 5G EVE Instantiated Experiment

- To start executing tests on the instantiated experiment, click on the icon indicated by the blue arrow in Figure 91.
- On clicking on that icon, you will be presented by two options i.e., “EXECUTE” or “TERMINATE” as shown in Figure 92.

Figure 92: 5G EVE Execute Experiment

- Select “EXECUTE” to start executing the test cases associated with your experiment. After selecting “EXECUTE”, you will be asked to input the name of your execution, so do it and then click submit to start running your tests.
- When the experiment is executing, the experiment status will change to “EXECUTING” as indicated in Figure 93.

Figure 93: 5G EVE Experiment Execution Running

A.10. 5G EVE PORTAL MONITORING & KPI REPORTING TOOLS

- As the experiment is running, you can view the monitoring metrics and 5G KPIs that you set in your context and experiment blueprints by clicking on the icon indicated by the blue arrow in Figure 93.
- For the simple Apache use case, the metrics and KPI graphs examples are given in Figure 94.

Figure 94: 5G EVE Simple Apache Use case KPI And Metrics Graphs

- Once the experiment has finished executing, the status will change from “*RUNNING EXECUTION*” back to “*INSTANTIATED*”. To view the experiment tests details, click on “eye” icon as indicated in Figure 95.

Id	Descriptor Id	Sites	Status	Execution Status
1	Test	SPAIN_STONIC	INSTANTIATED	
3	apache_exp_27_05	SPAIN_STONIC	INSTANTIATED	

Figure 95: 5G EVE View Experiment Tests Report

- On clicking the “eye” icon, you will be presented with some summary statistics about your experiment as shown in Figure 96.

Figure 96: 5G EVE Experiment Tests Summary

- To view the 5G EVE KPIs validation report for the tests carried out in your experiment, please click on the “Report” icon as shown in Figure 96. Clicking on this icon, for this simple use case, the validation report looks similar to the one indicated in Figure 97.

Figure 97: 5G EVE KPI Validation Report

- As you can see in Figure 97, the validated KPI, i.e., *requests_time_taken_kpi*, is the KPI that you set when creating the experiment blueprint.
- We can see that the KPI validation failed because we set the upper threshold (i.e., time taken by the requests KPI) to 40ms (refer to Figure 98), and although the average time per request was **35.2ms** as indicated in Figure 97, the maximum value is well beyond the KPI threshold, as shown in detail in Figure 98.

Figure 98: 5G EVE Simple Use Case 5G KPI Validation

- Finally, after executing your experiment and viewing the experiment report, don't forget to go back to the experiments page and “*terminate*” your experiment so that your allocated use case resources can be available to the other 5G EVE use cases.

A.10.1. 5G EVE Monitoring Platform DCS Component API

- The 5G EVE platform also provides the option of retrieving the monitoring metrics associated with a specific experimenter's experiments using API calls.
- To retrieve these metrics using the REST API, an experimenter needs to first obtain an authentication token from the 5G EVE Role-based Access control (RBAC) component and the experiment Id of the executed experiment.
- Upon receiving the authentication token and the experiment ID, the experimenter can use the 5G EVE Data Collection and Storage (DCS) API to retrieve the metrics and KPI data.
- In the proceeding sections, we will discuss how to retrieve the authentication token and the experiment Id. Finally, we will look at some example API calls and responses to retrieve the metrics and KPI data.

A.10.1.1. Obtain an Authentication token

- An authentication token can be obtained using the REST API of the 5G EVE RBAC component [1].
- For example, to obtain an authentication token, an API request similar to this would work; remember to replace the email and password with your actual credentials:

```
curl --location --request POST 'https://portal.5g-eve.eu/portal/rbac/login' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--data-raw '{
  "email": "abc@abc.com", "password": "xyzyzy"}'
```

- If the request is successful, you will be presented with an access token and a refresh token, something similar to the ones below:

```
{
```

```
"access_token":
"eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCIgOiAiSldUIiwia2lkIiA6ICJQS1Q1Q3Y3cVNwejlYUj1TXJmQVh
NWVdBc..... ",

"refresh_token":
"eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cCIgOiAiSldUIiwia2lkIiA6ICI1YTc1MDk5OC04NjQ2LTQwODItODh
hMS1iZDg2NmQyZGZiYzciQ..... ",

"username": "abc@abc.com"
}
```

- Next, we shall proceed to obtain the experiment ID.

A.10.1.2. Obtain the Experiment ID

- To obtain the experiment ID, we must interact with the REST API of the 5G EVE Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) component [2].
- So, by using the access token obtained from section A.10.1.1 above, we can make the following request to the ELM component to obtain the experiment id associated with our experiment descriptor id. The experiment descriptor id can be obtained from the portal, as illustrated in **Figure 99**.

Figure 99: Obtain the Experiment Descriptor ID from the 5G EVE portal

- For example, to obtain the experiment ID for the experiment descriptor ID “3137” highlighted in **Figure 99** above, we can make a request similar to this:

```
curl --location --request GET 'https://portal.5g-eve.eu/portal/elm/experiment?experimentDescriptorId=3137' \
--header 'Authorization: Bearer eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCIgOiAiSldUIiwia2lkIiA6ICJQS1Q1Q3Y3cVNwejlYUj1TXJmQVhNWVdBcUJfNkplaFncEILR3V5Vkm0In0 ' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--header 'Cookie: JSESSIONID=CB9F5DDEC96AAE9CBBFE80EEE9414F1F' \
--data-raw '{
```



```
--header 'Cookie: JSESSIONID=19B575C23684DE1A8827D47B8B73E577' \
--data-raw '{
  "email": "abc@abc.com",
  "password": "xyzxzzz"
}'
```

Note: the authentication token has been truncated here for readability's sake

- If the request is successful, then you will be presented with a list of topics associated to the experiment. For this experiment we only have one topic i.e., test_prod_v2.e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7.spain_5tonic.application_metric.apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken
- Finally, we can retrieve either the metrics or the KPI data published to a particular topic by specifying the topic id in the request, something similar to the request below.

```
curl --location --request GET 'https://portal.5g-eve.eu/portal/dcs/topics/e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7/test_prod_v2.e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7.spain_5tonic.application_metric.apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken' \
--header 'Authorization: Bearer eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXLTUwLWVudC5cIiwiaWF0IjoiYXZlbnR5c3Y3cVNwejl5YUJ1TXJmQVh' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--header 'Cookie: JSESSIONID=19B575C23684DE1A8827D47B8B73E577' \
--data-raw '{
  "email": "superusertest@mail.com",
  "password": "123456"
}'
```

Note: the authentication token has been truncated here for readability's sake

- If the request is successful, then you will be able to view all the metric data that is currently published in that topic.
- It is possible also using Postman (or any other tool with a GUI) to interact with the DCS API, if the experimenter does not feel comfortable with command line.

A.11. KPI VALIDATION

- After the experiment execution is finished, the validation report is generated and available to the vertical using the button shown in A.10 following the steps in Figure 100 and Figure 101.
- The validation report is split in six segments.
- First there is a list of all the experiments the vertical has created and executed, as seen in Figure 100.

Figure 100: Experiment list for the vertical

- There is also a list of testcases for each experiment. Selecting a different testcase will display the KPIs and KPI performance graphs related to that specific testcase, visible in Figure 101.

Figure 101: Test cases list for the experiment

- Then, there is a segment that contains general experiment information like the use case, the site where it is deployed and the date/time the experiment started and finished. This can be viewed in Figure 102.

Figure 102: General experiment information

- Next, shown in Figure 103, there is a part with the description of the specific test case and specifically the validated KPIs and the validation conditions.

Figure 103: Testcase information

- The first part of the report showing the actual results of validation process, Figure 104, includes statistics for the KPIs of each testcase, such as min, max and average value, along with the result of that specific KPI validation. The total of successful and failed testcases is also displayed.

Figure 104: Test case summary

- Scrolling down, the final part of the report can be found, as shown in Figure 105, which includes information regarding the behaviour of the KPI during the whole execution of the experiment.

Figure 105: KPI performance

A.12. PERFORMANCE DIAGNOSIS

- After the experiment execution is finished, the performance diagnosis results are added in the validation report and the final report is generated.

A.12.1 Naming conventions

- In order for the mapping of the metrics to the nodes of the NS to be correct, a few naming conventions must be honoured. This means that the name of the nodes declared in all the Blueprints, Descriptors and during the experiment creation stage must be consistent, as shown in the descriptor for the Simple Apache use case in Figure 106. Also, the name of the metrics must be prefixed with the name of the node generating them, like in Figure 107.

```
VNFD w/ Id: be55660e-8961-11ea-bc55-0242ac130003

  maxNumberOfInstances: 1
  capabilities:
    virtualCompute:
      properties:
        virtualMemory:
          virtualMemSize: 1024
          numaEnabled: false
        virtualCpu:
          numVirtualCpu: 1
  requirements:
    virtualStorage:
      - apache_client_vnf_storage
  apache_client_vnf_VNF:
    type: toska.nodes.nfv.VNF
    properties:
      descriptorId: be55660e-8961-11ea-bc55-0242ac130003
      descriptorVersion: '1.0'
      provider: UC3M
      productName: apache_client_vnf
      softwareVersion: '1.0'
      productInfoName: apache_client_vnf
      productInfoDescription: apache_client_vnf
      flavourId: apache_client_vnf_flavor
      flavourDescription: apache_client_vnf flavor
```

Figure 106: TOSCA descriptor of a sample NSD

```

"topics" : [
  {
    "brokerAddr" : "172.17.73.103:9092",
    "topic" : "Simple_UC.70f91b38-5c56-466b-a42f-606ae0bcc528.spain_5tonic.application_metric_apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken",
    "metric" : "apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken"
  }
],
"publish" : [
  {
    "brokerAddr" : "172.17.73.103:9092",
    "topic" : "Simple_UC.70f91b38-5c56-466b-a42f-606ae0bcc528.spain_5tonic.kpi.apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken_kpi",
    "kpi" : "apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken_kpi",
    "unit" : "s",
    "input" : [
      "apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken"
    ],
    "formula" : "apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken",
    "interval" : 1.0,
    "lowerBound" : "5",
    "upperBound" : "40"
  }
]

```

Figure 107: Configuration of the RAV by the EEM for the Simple Apache use case

A.12.2 Activation

- After the experiment has been instantiated, upon requesting the experiment execution, the Vertical is presented with the option, shown in Figure 108, to enable performance diagnosis for this specific experiment.

Figure 108: Performance diagnosis activation option

A.12.3 Performance diagnosis report

- After the performance diagnosis workflow has finished, the results are added into the validation report in order to complete the final report for the vertical.
- The additions to the final report are four new segments.
- First, a timeline graph, seen in Figure 109, of the performance of each node of the examined service showing the behaviour of each these nodes during the experiment execution. Node status is characterized as spike when abnormal metric values are received for a brief period, based on the interval of the metric collection. A node is assigned the unhealthy status when those abnormal values persist for multiple collected metrics instances. Identifying the abnormal behaviour of nodes can help the experimenter pinpoint the specific action that might have caused in conjunction with the time frame that it happened.

Figure 109: Node status timeline

- Next, a network graph, as in Figure 110, showing the service topology is included together with a slider that shifts through the various timestamps on which the metrics were examined. Selecting different timestamps, shifts the status of each node to its monitored status during that timestamp.

Figure 110: Topology network graph

- When a node flagged as unhealthy is selected on the topology graph, a new bar chart, visible in Figure 111, appears to show which impact of each measured metric and KPI related to the node has to its status being flagged as unhealthy. This is an extension of the status analysis for the nodes. It provides insight on which metrics show abnormal behaviour and at what degree do they impact the final status assignment.

Figure 111: Metrics/KPIs impact on node status

- Finally, the last graph, in Figure 112, shows the performance of the KPIs for each unique combination of resources that the experiment has run on. In this way, the vertical can cross-compare the performance of the service on different deployments and receive insights regarding improvements or degradation of performance caused by the different resource allocation. Combining this with a cost analysis for each set of resources can provide valuable information to vertical.

Figure 112: Comparison of different deployments

A.13. TROUBLE-SHOOTING TIPS

In this section, we present some tips to help you troubleshoot in case you run into some issues when designing, deploying, and executing your experiments on the 5G EVE platform:

A.13.1. COMMON GUIDELINES

- Make sure you have converted all YAML descriptor files to JSON before uploading.
- Each blueprint needs to have a corresponding NSD in IFA14 format.
- Ensure that all the blueprint and nsd ids are in UUID format.
- Make sure that your nsd descriptor files begin with the “*nsd_content*” parameter.
- For all the descriptors, use the experiment descriptor wizard on the 5G EVE portal to help you create the vertical service, context, test-case and experimental descriptors by inputting each of the parameters’ the exact values listed in the blueprints.

A.13.2. ISSUES SUBMITTING YOUR BLUEPRINTS

- Currently, the portal has integrated the “blueprint validator tool” that will be able to capture most of errors associated with submission of your blueprints and readily avail them.

A.13.3. ISSUES VIEWING YOUR BLUEPRINTS

- In this case, the issue is most probably related to your uploaded Blueprint.
- Always use the eye icon to check if your descriptors have been appropriately loaded. If you can’t view your descriptor, there may be something missing /wrongly filled in your Blueprint. However, if this the case, the “blueprint validator tool” will inform you of the error during blueprint upload.
- Watch out for the name and version of each Blueprint you upload. There can only be one name and version match.
- Inside the VSB blueprint, please ensure that the “*compatibleContextBlueprint*” parameter has UUIDs instead of the context blueprint names.
- For the Experiment Blueprint, use the portal to guide you.

A.13.4. SUBMISSION OF A TICKET TO THE 5G EVE PORTAL

- If none of the above troubleshooting tips work for you or your issue is not related to any of the above issues, then, in that case, you can submit a ticket to the 5G EVE portal by clicking on the “tickets” section anywhere you are on the portal as illustrated in Figure 113.

Figure 113: 5G EVE Submit Ticket

- As you can see from Figure 113, no matter where you are on the portal, you can just click on “Tickets” to submit a ticket or report a bug on the portal.
- On clicking on “tickets,” you will be presented with a page similar to the one in Figure 114. Click on the “+” icon to create a new ticket, as indicated in Figure 114.

Id	Product	Component	Status	Summary	Actions
282	SPAIN_STONIC	EXPERIMENT_SCHEDULE	CONFIRMED	apache_exec_27_05 SLOT_REQUEST	[edit] [delete]
281	5G-EVE_PORTAL	AUTHENTICATION	CONFIRMED	Testeando desde GUI	[edit] [delete]
280	5G-EVE_PORTAL	AUTHENTICATION	CONFIRMED	testing exp_dev tickets	[edit] [delete]
279	5G-EVE_PORTAL	AUTHENTICATION	CONFIRMED	Ticket from gui	[edit] [delete]
271	SPAIN_STONIC	EXPERIMENT_SCHEDULE	CONFIRMED	Test SLOT_REQUEST	[edit] [delete]
270	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File testing from gui correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]
269	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File testing from gui correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]
268	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File with space correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]
267	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File testing correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]
266	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File testing correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]

Figure 114: 5G EVE Tickets Page

- On clicking on the “+” icon, you will be presented with a page similar to Figure 115, so go ahead and select the 5G EVE product and component where you got the error by using the “arrow” buttons as shown in Figure 115. Provide a summary & description of your problem and select the admin user to assign the ticket to. Once done, click on “Create,” and an email will be sent to the assigned admin user, and your ticket will be handled as soon as possible.

Figure 115: 5G EVE Create New Ticket

- An example of a filled-in ticket is given in Figure 116.

Figure 116: 5G EVE Filed Ticket

- Once you are done filing your ticket, you can confirm that your ticket has been successfully created by looking at the new list of tickets and your ticket should be there.